

in the peak of the simulated BPH population (Fig. 2).

The role of the model is to formulate explicit hypotheses that describe important parameters affecting BPH population dynamics. These parameters can be used to identify potential strategies for improved BPH management. *S*

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2. Simulation of BPH population changes at the first test site (—) compared with the observed population (•). Simulation of BPH population when predation is reduced by 50% (----).

Pest Control and Management WEEDS

Salvinia molesta found in Philippine rice fields

K. Moody, J. P. Descalsota, P. C. Gonzales, and V. N. Cacnio, IRRI

Salvinia molesta D. S. Mitchell, a free-floating, mat-forming, perennial fern, which reproduces vegetatively at an alarming rate, has been found in transplanted rice (Fig. 1) and drainage canals in Iloilo Province, Panay Island, Philippines. *S. molesta* is a native of Brazil and has become a serious weed in most countries where it has been introduced.

Individual plants are up to 30 cm long and have many leaves (Fig. 2). Each node of the slender stem produces three leaves. Two are green and floating and one is brown, root-like, and submerged. The floating leaves of young plants are round to oval, 0.5-2.0 cm long, and lie flat on the water surface. With age and

1. *Salvinia molesta* growing in transplanted rice in the Philippines.

crowding, they become two-lobed, folded sharply along the midrib, 2.0-3.5 cm

long, and only the midrib is in contact with the water. The submerged leaf is

much divided and from 5 to 25 cm long. Sporocarps are 2 to 3 mm in diameter and sterile. They are found on parts of the submerged leaves.

To our knowledge, this is the first time the weed has been found in rice in the Philippines. *S*

2. Diagram showing floating leaves, submerged leaves, and sporocarps of *S. molesta*.

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Herbicides for weed control in rice nurseries

C.L. Patel, Z.G. Patel, R.B. Patel, and H.R. Patel, Agronomy Department, Gujarat Agricultural University (GAU), Navsari 396450, India

Effect of herbicide treatments on weed dry weight and rice seedling dry matter yield at 26 d after sowing, Naysari, India.

Treatment ^a	Weed dry wt (g/m ²)	Seedling dry matter yield (g/m ²)
Unweeded control	31	29
Hand weeding 15 DAS	8	47
Propanil 2.0 kg/ha	17	34
Thiobencarb (kg ai/ha)		
1.0	16	32
1.5	16	33
2.0	12	37
Butachlor (kg ai/ha)		
1.0	18	33
1.5	10	34
2.0	9	36
Pendimethalin (kg ai/ha)		
1.0	19	34
1.5	10	44
2.0	6	47
CD at 5%	3	6

^aDAS = days after sowing.

We evaluated five herbicides and application rates for controlling weeds in an IR22 nursery at GAU Farm in 1984 kharif (Jun-Nov). Thiobencarb, butachlor, and pendimethalin were applied at different doses 5 d after sowing, and propanil was applied 15 d after sowing. Samples of weeds and rice seedlings were collected from a 1-m² area 26 d after sowing and dry weight was recorded. Weeds were *Cyperus difformis* and *C. iria* (53%), *Echinochloa spp.* (41%), and *Eclipta alba* (6%).

Butachlor controlled sedges and

pendimethalin controlled monocots. Higher doses of all the herbicides were more effective than lower doses. Only propanil was phytotoxic, causing slight leaf tip burning.

Weed dry weight and dry matter yield of rice seedlings showed a significant negative correlation ($r = -0.73$). Lowest weed dry weight (6 g/m²) and highest seedling dry matter yield (47 g/m²) were with pendimethalin at 2.0 kg ai/ha, closely followed by hand weeding (see table). *S*

Soil and Crop Management

Effect of harvest time on IR44 ratoon grain yield

J. S. Chauhan, F. S. S. Lopez, and B. S. Vergara, IRRI

Ratoon crop duration is very important for ratoon grain yield. Although an

advantage of a ratoon crop is its short growth duration, sometimes duration is too short for tillers to produce enough leaf area to support a well-filled panicle. The result is low ratoon grain yields. Relatively longer ratoon crop duration contributes to higher grain yield, but if